

COMPOUNDS OF SILICON TETRACHLORIDE WITH AMINES AND HETEROCYCLIC BASES

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Several derivatives of silicon tetrachloride have been prepared by the action of primary (mono & di), secondary and tertiary amines and heterocyclic bases on SiCl_4 , and their properties studied and structures discussed.

A general survey of the literature shows that very little work has been done on the formation of compounds of SiF_4 and SiCl_4 with amines and heterocyclic bases.

With SiCl_4 and aniline, Girard and Pabst (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1880, 34, 38) obtained violaniline and triphenylamine blue and Harold (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1898, 20, 13), SiCl_4 .(4 aniline). Hardens (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1887, 81, 47) prepared $\text{SiCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Py}$ and $\text{SiCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N}$ with pyridine and quinoline. Schick and Degering (*Chem. Abs.*, 1950, 44, 4283^b) have shown that SiCl_4 affords condensation products with 1:3-diaminobutane and with tetraethylenepentamine. Trost (*ibid.*, 1952, 46, 2945^a) showed that SiCl_4 formed precipitates with a large number of organic compounds. Breederveld and Watermann (*Research*, London, 1954, 7, 55) obtained $\text{PhEtN} \cdot \text{SiCl}_4$ and $(\text{PhEtN})_2 \cdot \text{SiCl}_4$ by the action of SiCl_4 on diisopropylamine and ethylanilino group respectively.

The present investigation was therefore undertaken with a view to studying the preparation and properties of these compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL

The amine and SiCl_4 used were of B.D.H. 'pure' quality and ether was distilled over metallic sodium. Benzene or ether was used as the solvent as SiCl_4 was very reactive and formed substituted compounds with alcohol.

In the case of primary amines, ether was used as the solvent since the compounds formed were partly soluble in benzene. For the rest, benzene was used as the solvent.

SiCl_4 and the organic compounds were dissolved in the respective solvents separately and cooled in ice. The amine solution was added slowly to SiCl_4 solution when a precipitate was formed immediately, but there was a great evolution of heat and, hence, the mixture was cooled in ice.

The precipitate obtained was filtered, washed free of the amine, and dried. It was analysed and its properties studied.

Silicon was estimated as SiO_2 and chlorine as AgCl . In four cases nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method and in the rest, the organic matter was found by difference.

The co-ordination number of silicon in the cases studied is six or eight and therefore the effective atomic number does not assume its inert gas configuration.

TABLE I

Name.	Compound formed.	Colour.	M.P.	%Silicon.		%Chlorine.		%Organic matter.		%Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Primary amines:											
1.	Naphthylamine	Deep Orangeish yellow	140.8°	3.85	3.78	19.14	19.14	77.01	77.08	7.60	7.54
2.	Naphthylamine Do		156.0°	3.82	3.78	19.47	19.14	77.71	77.08	7.42	7.54
3.	p-Toluidine	Fale violet	145.0°	4.80	4.68	24.15	23.74	71.05	71.58	9.30	9.36
4.	m- " "	White	160.0°	4.68	4.68	24.20	23.74	71.12	71.58	9.28	9.36
5.	Benzylamine	White	90.0°	4.80	4.68	23.10	23.74	72.10	71.58		
6.	o-Phenetidine	Violet	105.5°	4.04	3.90	20.26	19.78	75.70	76.32		
7.	p- " "	Violet	108.0°	4.03	3.90	20.27	19.78	75.70	76.32		
8.	o-Anisidine	Dirty violet	100.0°	4.26	4.23	21.22	21.45	74.52	74.32		
9.	p- " "	White	160.0°	4.25	4.23	20.89	21.45	74.85	74.32		
Secondary amines:											
10.	o-Methyltoluidine	Yellow	168.0°	7.01	6.79	31.69	34.45	58.30	58.75		
11.	Benzylamine	Yellow	105.0°	5.75	5.20	26.01	26.50	68.24	68.30		
Tertiary amines:											
12.	Trimethylamine	White	102.0°	9.78	9.72	49.44	49.30	41.78	40.98		
13.	Benzyldecylaniline	Yellow	100.0°	5.75	5.26	26.92	26.69	67.33	68.05		
Dianilines:											
14.	Tolidine	Pink-orange	199.0°	4.20	4.71	24.60	23.91	71.20	71.38		
15.	Benzydine	Ash coloured	184.0°	5.30	5.20	25.70	26.39	69.00	68.41		
16.	D'ansidine	Dirty violet	140.0°	4.57	4.25	21.90	21.56	73.53	74.19		
17.	Rhylene-diamine	Cream white	189.0°	9.30	9.65	48.50	48.97	42.20	41.38		
18.	Quinoline	White	119.0°	4.09	4.08	20.90	20.70	75.01	76.22		

Almost all the compounds are semicrystalline powder and are stable in dry air or in anhydrous inert solvents, but begin to hydrolyse slowly as soon as these come in contact with water or sodium hydroxide solution.

When heated, these compounds decompose before melting. The compounds obtained with the diamines are more stable and hydrolyse slowly.

It has been found that 4 molecules of primary amines and heterocyclic bases and two of diamines attach themselves to the central atom, chelate compounds being formed in the case of diamines, which is responsible for the greater stability of these compounds.

In the case of secondary and tertiary amines, only two molecules are attached to the central atom, which is probably due to the weak co-ordinating power of the $-\text{NH}=\text{}$ and $-\text{N}\equiv$ groups.

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